

DETERMINANTS OF MENSTRUAL HYGIENE KNOWLEDGE, AND PRACTICE AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ABIA SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT

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Abstract: The aim of the study was to investigate the socio-demographic determinants of menstrual hygiene knowledge, availability and practice among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District. Descriptive research design was used with population of 1446 senior secondary school students. Self- structure questionnaires and a sample size of 1000 were utilized. The result showed 79.4% students had good knowledge of menstrual hygiene, indicating those whose age ranges from (15-19 years; 81.3%), and students in SS2 (80.7%) had good knowledge of menstrual hygiene among others. ($\bar{X}=2.47$, $SD=0.96$) revealed unavailability of menstrual hygiene facilities needed in schools. Also, the grand mean of ($\bar{X}=2.34$, $SD=1.01$) had a low extent of practice, students whose age ranges from (10-14 years; $\bar{X}= 2.36$, $SD=0.98$), and SS2 students with ($\bar{X}= 2.41$, $SD=1.01$) had more practice among others and yet low. However, age, class of study had significant relationship with menstrual hygiene knowledge and practice among senior secondary school students in Abia South senatorial districts. It was concluded that secondary school students in Abia South had good knowledge of menstrual hygiene, unavailability of menstrual facilities and low practice level. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that governments, non-governmental organization (NGO) and individuals can take up project of providing menstrual facilities in different public schools, such as borehole water, soap, menstrual pads, more toilets, changing rooms, also incinerators as such will improve availability and practice of menstrual hygiene among senior secondary school students in Abia South.

Introduction

In low-income countries, women's choices of menstrual hygiene materials are often limited by the costs, availability and social norms. According to the World Health Organization, as of 2018 there are about 1.9 billion women who are of reproductive age. Not only are women's choices limited but, World Health Organisation (WHO) and United Nations International Children's Emergency Funds UNICEF, 780 million people do not have access to improved water sources and about 2.5 billion people lack access to improved sanitation. The lack of proper hygiene leads to a harder time for women to manage feminine hygiene (UNESCO, 2014; Kaur et al., 2018). This neglected public health, social and educational issues require prioritization, coordination and investment (Sommer, 2016). In Nigeria, especially among schoolgirls and women, there is a culture of silence and shame regarding issues of sexuality and menstruation that are attributed to cultural restrictions. These prevent sufficient information from reaching girls and women (Onyegegbu, 2014).

Aniebue (2009) reported that mothers do not educate their daughters about the onset of menstruation, its duration, or healthy practices. Girls often seek information from their peers, friends, or siblings who provide them with superstitious and incorrect information which leads to fear and anxiety among the girls. Aluko (2014) described the consequences attached to this biological phenomenon as unfair and unjust. However, the mothers admit not

knowing much correct information to transmit (Onyegegbu, 2014). Multiple research findings to date in Nigeria have demonstrated varying perceptions, beliefs, knowledge, attitudes and practices related to menstrual hygiene.

Menstruation can also be called monthly period which is the regular discharge or flow of blood and mucosal tissue from the inner lining of the uterus through the vagina (Women's Gynecologic Health, 2011). Each month, the female body prepares itself for a possible pregnancy. The uterus develops a thicker lining, and the ovaries release an egg that can be fertilized by sperm. Periods will continue regularly (usually monthly) until menopause. The first period, is a point in time known as menarche, which usually begins between the ages of 12 and 15 years (Prajapati & Kedia, 2015).

Menstrual hygiene management was defined by the Joint Monitoring Program (JMP, 2012) for Water Supply, Sanitation and Hygiene as Women and adolescent girls using a clean menstrual management material to absorb or collect blood that can be changed in privacy as often as necessary for the duration of the menstruation period, using soap and water for washing the body as required, and having access to facilities to dispose of used menstrual management materials. They understand the basic facts linked to the menstrual cycle and how to manage it with dignity and without discomfort or fear (WHO/UNICEF, 2012). Despite the fact that menstruation is a normal physiological process in females, it is not easy

for every adolescent girl to maintain good hygiene (Mahon & Fernandes, 2010).

The Center for Diseases Control and Prevention (2017) defined hygiene as behaviors that can improve cleanliness and lead to good health, such as frequent hand washing, face washing and bathing with soap and water. Hygiene in a variety of settings plays an important role in preventing the spread of infectious diseases (Bloomfield et al., 2009). Good hygiene is an effective barrier to many infectious diseases, and improves health and well-being. Improvements in hygiene should be made alongside improvements in water supply and sanitation, and integrated with other interventions, such as improving nutrition and increasing incomes. There is the belief that menstruation is an unclean and secret issue which should not be discussed. Some of these student are absent from school because they are menstruating. They are not permitted to collect water from the public ponds especially traditional sources. They are not allowed to perform certain religious rites (United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), Global Health Awareness Research Foundation (GHARF) Report, 2008). Furthermore, research finding showed that girls' capacity to manage their periods is affected by lack of access to affordable hygienic sanitary materials, disposal options for used materials, adequate water supply, clean toilets, hand washing facilities and access to changing rooms. If these facilities are not always available in school, it exposes many girls to manage their periods with great discomfort and unhygienic conditions (Olukanni, 2013).

The socio demographic determinant reviewed showed that Age has influence on menstrual hygiene, in a study by Habtegiorgis et al. (2021) noted that girls 16–19 years old were 1.9 times more likely to have good menstrual hygiene Practices than girls in the 13–15 years age group (AOR = 1.93, 95% CI: [1.22–3.06]). This might be because, the higher age range (16-19) of the teenagers have been more exposed or have gotten more information either by parents, friends or the media than the lower age range (13-15) that are finding it difficult to ask questions or they are still hiding to avoid people from knowing that they are menstruating. Grade 10 students were 1.9 times more likely to have good menstrual hygiene practices than Grade 9 students [AOR= (1.90, 95% CI: [1.18–3.07]) (Habtegiorgis et al., 2021). This showed that the class of students influenced menstrual hygiene. This is because the higher the students class the higher knowledge and exposure. Parents has a role to play in menstrual hygiene, in a Ghanaian study, less than 10% of the adolescent girls receive menstrual education from health providers, compared to 80% who receive menstrual education from their parents (Gumanga & Kwame-Aryee, 2013). Bekkalale et al. (2014) they noted that among 184 respondents, Mothers were the first informants in about 56.5% girls. A Ugandan study demonstrates that most girls from poor urban settings learn about menstruation from their peers and sisters, while the majority of girls from rural areas receive information from their mothers. Findings suggest that the rural mothers feel more comfortable discussing

menstruation with their daughters than the urban poor mothers who typically stay silent (Matovu, 2013). This showed that parents has a lot of role to play in the aspect of menstrual hygiene, in the other way round the information that is coming mainly from parents will make menstrual hygiene knowledge to be limited to the secondary school girls, but when they are also receiving information from other reliable means like, teachers, media, and other professionals, this will improve the accurate knowledge and practice of menstrual hygiene.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to investigate the determinants of knowledge and practice of menstrual hygiene among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to determine the:

1. Menstrual hygiene knowledge among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District.
2. Availability of menstrual hygiene facilities among senior secondary schools in Abia South Senatorial District.
3. Practice of menstrual hygiene among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District.
4. Knowledge and practice of menstrual hygiene based on age among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District.
5. Knowledge and practice of menstrual hygiene based on class of study among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District.

METHODOLOGY

The area of study was Abia South Senatorial District; Abia State is a state in the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The research design used in this study was the descriptive cross sectional research study. The population of study consisted of all senior secondary students in Abia South, it has 76 public secondary schools. The total number of female students were two thousand two hundred and fifty five (2255), while twenty eight selected schools for this study were a total number of one thousand four hundred and forty six (1446) (Secondary School Management Education board Abia State, 2022).

The sample size in this study was statistically determined using Taro Yamane Formula which gave 313. However, in other to have a representative of the total population from the seven Local Government Areas, the sample size was increased to one thousand (1000).

Research instrument for data collection was self-structured questionnaire. A four-part questionnaire was developed. Part A consisted of socio demographic data which has age, class of study. Part B captioned availability of menstrual hygiene facilitates, part C included the Knowledge of menstrual hygiene, Part D was the level of practice of menstrual hygiene. The reliability of the instrument for availability of facilities needed in schools showed 0.810 using crobach Alpha while the responses were subjected to Kuder Richardson for knowledge questions which yielded 0.815 and Cronbach

alphafor practice questions which was 0.825 to establish the reliability of the instrument. The data collected from the questionnaire survey were carefully coded and analyzed using statistical product and service solution (SPSS) version 23.0.

RESULTS

The results of the analysed data showed;

Research Question 1: What is the level of knowledge of menstrual hygiene among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District?

Table 1.1: Knowledge of menstrual hygiene among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District.

SN	Items	Yes F(%)	No F(%)	Decision
1	Menstruation is the monthly discharge of blood through the vagina	972(100)	0(0.00)	Good
2	Menarche is defined as the first menstrual period in a female adolescent	723(74.4)	249(25.6)	Good
3	Availability of Water, soap, clean toilets, clean changing room, sanitary pads and sex education in school can promote good menstrual hygiene	911(93.7)	61(6.30)	Good
4	Poor menstrual hygiene can result to infection	967(99.5)	5(0.5)	Good
5	Sex education is the provision of knowledge about body development, sex, sexuality, and relationship	705(72.5)	267(27.5)	Good
6	Sanitary pad can be used during menstruation for good hygiene	968(99.6)	4(0.4)	Good
7	Having a bath at least twice when menstruating is good to maintain good hygiene during menstruation	970(99.8)	2(0.2)	Good
8	Pads should be changed every six to eight hours	968(99.6)	4(0.4)	Good
9	The use of tissue paper, cotton wool during menstruation is not safe	93(9.6)	879(90.4)	Poor
10	Proper drying of washed re-usable (thick clean white towel) materials in direct sunlight is safe	261(26.9)	711(73.1)	Poor
11	Used menstrual pads should be properly wrapped and safely disposed	705(72.5)	267(27.5)	Good
12	Flushing of menstrual materials can block the drainage system	889(91.5)	83(8.5)	Good
13	Incinerator is a furnace for burning waste to ashes	839(86.3)	133(13.7)	Good

Grand total	772(79.4) 200(20.6) Good
Guide: ≥50% is good; <50% is poor knowledge F: Frequency	good knowledge while 200 (20.65) had poor knowledge of menstrual hygiene.
Table 1.1: Knowledge of menstrual hygiene among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District. The result established that more than three quarter 772(79.4%) had	Research question 2: Knowledge of menstrual hygiene based on age among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District?
Table 1.2: Age and knowledge of menstrual hygiene among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District.	

Age	Level of knowledge		Total F(%)	Decision
	Good F(%)	Poor F(%)		
10-14 years	204(74.7)	69(25.3)	273(100)	Good
15-19 years	558(81.3)	128(18.7)	686(100)	Good
20-24 years	10(76.9)	3(23.1)	13(100)	Good
Total	772(79.4)	200(20.6)	972(100)	Good

Table 1.2 revealed knowledge of menstrual hygiene based on age among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District. The result showed that good knowledge of menstrual hygiene was found more among those aged 15-19 years (81.3%), followed by those aged 20-24 years (76.9%) and those aged 10-14 years (74.7%). Good knowledge of

menstrual hygiene was found more among the older senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District.

Table 1.3: Class of study and knowledge of menstrual hygiene among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District.

Class of study	Level of knowledge		Total F(%)	Decision
	Good F(%)	Poor F(%)		
SS 1	233(76.6)	71(23.4)	304(100)	Good
SS 2	524(80.7)	125(19.3)	649(100)	Good
SS 3	15(78.9)	4(21.1)	19(100)	Good
Total	772(79.4)	200(20.6)	972(100)	Good

Table 1.3 revealed the knowledge of menstrual hygiene based on class of study among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District. The result showed that good knowledge of menstrual hygiene was found more among those in SS 2 (80.7%), followed by

those in SS 3 (78.9%) and those in SS 3 (76.6%). Good knowledge of menstrual hygiene was found more among the senior secondary school students in class 2 in Abia South Senatorial District.

Research Question 4: What is the level of availability of menstrual hygiene facilities among senior Secondary schools in Abia South Senatorial District?

Table 1.4: Summary of descriptive statistics on the level of availability of menstrual hygiene facilities in senior secondary schools in Abia South Senatorial District (n=972)

S/ N	ITEMS	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Not available	Mean	Decision
1	Borehole water.	290	56	210	416	2.77	Available
2	Soap.	316	58	138	460	2.76	Available
3	Clean female changing Rooms.	22	320	46	584	2.10	Not available
4	Clean female toilets.	298	38	116	520	2.88	Available
5	Sanitary pad.	86	94	270	522	2.11	Not available
6	Burning (Incinerator).	72	88	268	544	2.07	Not available
7	Sex education.	354	48	212	358	2.59	Available
Grand mean						2.47	Not Available

Criterion mean = 2.50. (from 2.50 and above is available while below 2.50 is not available)
 The result from Table 1.4 shows the descriptive statistics on the availability of menstrual hygiene facilities among senior secondary schools in Abia South Senatorial District. The grand mean shows an unavailability of

menstrual hygiene facilities among senior secondary schools in Abia South Senatorial District was found to be 2.47, SD=0.96.
Research Question 5: What is the extent of practice of menstrual hygiene among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District?

Table 1.5: Mean and Standard deviation showing extent of practice of menstrual hygiene among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District.

SN	Practice	\bar{X}	S. D.	Decision
1	Bath 3times daily when menstruating	3.90	.35	HE
2	Bath with soap and water during menstruation	2.28	1.38	LE
3	Washed private part clean with water	1.49	1.03	LE
4	Used tissue paper when menstruating	2.13	.98	LE
5	Used cotton wool when menstruating	2.39	.89	LE
6	Used thick clean white towel when menstruating	3.86	.39	HE
7	Used sanitary pad only when menstruating	1.42	1.00	LE
8	changed menstrual pads after 6 to 8 hours	3.49	1.47	HE
9	Properly washed hands with soap and water before and after changing menstrual absorbents	1.55	1.08	LE
10	Washed and dried reusable materials (thick clean white towel) in direct sunlight during school hours	2.58	1.42	HE
11	Disposed used menstrual materials at home from school	1.49	1.05	LE
12	Flushed used menstrual materials in the toilet	1.46	1.04	LE
13	Buried used menstrual materials after menstruating	1.34	.91	LE
14	Properly wrapped used menstrual materials in black nylon and dispose in a waste bin or in a burring furnace	3.39	1.13	HE
Grand mean		2.34	1.01	LE

Criterion mean = 2.50. Key: HE – high extent, LE = low extent

Table 1.5 showed the mean and standard deviation on extent of practice of menstrual hygiene among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District. The result revealed that the grand mean of 2.34±1.01 was less than the criterion mean of 2.50 which

indicates a low extent of practice. Thus, menstrual hygiene practice among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District was low.

Research Question 6: Practice of menstrual hygiene based on age among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District?

Table 1.6: Mean and Standard deviation showing extent of practice of menstrual hygiene based on age

SN	Practice	10-14yrs (N = 273)		15-19yrs (N = 686)		20-24yrs (N = 13)	
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD
1	Bath 3times daily when menstruating	3.91	.34	3.90	.34	3.84	.55
2	Bath with soap and water during menstruation	2.27	1.37	2.29	1.39	1.84	1.14
3	Washed private part clean with water	1.31	.87	1.55	1.08	1.61	.96
4	Used tissue paper when menstruating	3.57	1.04	3.64	.96	4.00	.00
5	Used cotton wool when menstruating	3.34	.96	3.41	.87	3.76	.83
6	Used thick clean white towel when menstruating	3.92	.27	3.38	.42	3.76	.43
7	Used sanitary pad only when menstruating	1.44	1.04	1.40	.96	2.38	1.55
8	changed menstrual pads after 6 to 8 hours	1.75	1.21	1.81	1.22	1.15	.37
9	Properly washed hands with soap and water before and after changing menstrual absorbents	1.53	1.09	1.54	1.07	2.15	1.51
10	Washed and dried reusable materials (thick clean white towel) in direct sunlight during school hours	2.50	1.45	2.62	1.41	1.69	1.11
11	Disposed used menstrual materials when home from school	1.41	1.01	1.53	1.08	1.46	.87
12	Flushed used menstrual materials in the toilet	1.51	1.10	1.43	1.00	2.15	1.51
13	Buried used menstrual materials after menstruating	1.32	.89	1.36	.83	1.00	.00
14	Properly wrapped used menstrual materials in black nylon and dispose in a waste bin or in a burring furnace	3.37	1.16	3.41	1.12	2.84	1.51
	Grand mean	2.36	.98	2.37	.98	2.40	.88

Criterion mean = 2.50. Key: HE – high extent, LE = low extent

Table 1.6 showed the mean and standard deviation on extent of practice of menstrual

hygiene based on age of respondents. The result revealed that those aged 20-24 years (2.40±0.88), followed by 15-19 years (2.37±0.98), and those 10-14 years (2.36±0.98). Thus, based on age, menstrual hygiene practice

was more among older senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District.

Research question 7: Practice of menstrual hygiene based on class of study among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District?

Table 1.7: Mean and Standard deviation showing extent of practice of menstrual hygiene based on class of study

SN	Practice items	SSS 1		SSS 2		SSS 3	
		(N = 304)	SD	(N = 649)	SD	(N = 19)	SD
		\bar{X}		\bar{X}		\bar{X}	
1	Bath 3times daily when menstruating	3.89	.36	3.91	.33	3.84	.35
2	Bath with soap and water during menstruation	2.34	1.37	2.27	1.40	1.84	1.16
3	Washed private part clean with water	1.32	.84	1.57	1.10	1.52	.90
4	Used tissue paper when menstruating	3.68	.92	3.61	1.01	3.57	1.02
5	Used cotton wool when menstruating	3.22	.99	3.47	.84	3.78	.71
6	Used thick clean white towel when menstruating	3.86	.39	3.86	.39	3.78	.41
7	Used sanitary pad only when menstruating	1.31	.89	1.44	1.01	2.77	1.47
8	changed menstrual pads after 6 to 8 hours	1.84	1.25	1.78	1.21	1.15	.37
9	Properly washed hands with soap and water before and after changing menstrual absorbents	1.35	.89	1.61	1.13	2.36	1.49
10	Washed and dried reusable materials (thick clean white towel) in direct sunlight during school hours	2.69	1.43	2.55	1.41	1.50	.98
11	Disposed used menstrual materials when home from school	1.35	.91	1.56	1.12	1.52	.96
12	Flushed used menstrual materials in the toilet	1.42	1.01	1.47	1.04	2.15	1.46
13	Buried used menstrual materials after menstruating	1.35	.89	1.35	.94	1.05	.22

14	Properly wrapped used menstrual materials in black nylon and dispose in a waste bin or in a burring furnace	3.46	1.04	3.38	1.15	2.68	1.49
Grand mean		2.36	.94	2.41	1.01	2.39	.92

Criterion mean = 2.50. Key: HE – high extent, LE = low extent

Table 1.7 showed the mean and standard deviation on extent of practice of menstrual hygiene based on class of study. The result revealed that those in SS 2 (2.41±1.01), followed by those in SS 3 (2.39±0.92), and those in SS 1 (2.36±0.94). Thus, based on class of study, menstrual hygiene practice was more among those in Senior class (SS2) in Abia South Senatorial District.

Discussion of Findings

Good knowledge about menstrual hygiene among senior secondary schools in Abia South Senatorial District was indicated in the study, this got a lot of support by Buradum et al. (2020), Bindu and Rohini (2019), Eleen et al. (2018), Gultie et al. (2013), Funmito et al. (2017), Budhathoki et al. (2018), Upashe et al. (2015), these must be as a result of all hands on deck regarding menstrual hygiene. In their study, indicated that most girls used reusable cloth which was also supported by this study, this may be as a result of high cost of sanitary pads. Mohammed and Larsen-Reindorf (2020), Belayneh and Mekuriaw (2019), Rajanbir et al. (2018), Jagruti and Riddhi (2015), showed poor knowledge about menstruation which was not in support in this study, socio demographic factors, showed that girls in their late adolescents were less likely to have poor menstrual knowledge compared to those aged

10–14 years (AOR 0.20, 95%CI 0.08–0.48). This showed support in this study, aged 15-19 years were 1.23 times more likely to be knowledgeable (OR = 1.23, 95%CI: 1.18 – 1.27). Compared to those aged 10-14 years. Reason was that the higher the age the more information they have gained.

The findings on the availability of menstrual hygiene facilities among senior secondary schools in Abia South Senatorial District showed that menstrual hygiene facilities were not available in the schools, this findings have been found to receive support from the study of Maxwell et al. (2020), Sivakami et al. (2019), Chinyama et al. (2019), Ahmed et al. (2018), Boosey et al. (2014), who also found out that the respondents reported a lack of access to adequate resources, facilities and accurate information to manage their menstrual hygiene effectively in school, these may be as a result of neglect by the governments, NGOs and some individuals who are capable of making constant provision of the needs in our secondary schools. Hussein, (2020) had good knowledge about menstruation also good menstrual hygiene management practices while practice in this study was low, this may be reasons due to unavailability of menstrual hygiene facilities in school which was seen in this study. This shows that information was more among the learned which led to practice. Habtegiorgis et al. (2021), Shallo et al. (2020), Chet (2020), Hala (2020)

Budhathoki et al. (2018) had good menstrual hygiene practice but this study showed low menstrual hygiene practice this may be as a result of unavailability of menstrual hygiene facilities needed in school which was clearly revealed in this study. Omidvar and Begum (2010), Frequency of changing pads was 2-3 times a day by girls, which was in line with this study. It can be perceived that two-thirds of the selected girls (68.9%) regardless of age used disposable pads, in this study was contrast where disposable pad was used at a very low extent, this was as a result of high cost of disposable pad. Since significant associations were also found between age and practice of storage ($P= 0.002$) this was also supported by this study which showed a significant association between age and practice menstrual hygiene ($P= 0.00$). Poor menstrual hygiene practice was seen in this study, which was in line with studies by Hussein (2020), Maxwell et al. (2020), Belayneh and Mekuriaw (2019), Funmito et al. (2017), and Upashe et al. (2015), more than three-fourths (79.8%) of the good MHM group washed their hands with water and soap after changing their sanitary materials this was not true in this study which showed very few persons (1.55) wash their hands before and after changing menstrual absorbent. In his study noted that none had soap for cleaning and washing purposes, but this study noted availability of soap this may be as results were students are to submit soaps to their teachers every term. Hala (2020), Budhathoki et al. (2018) in their study noted that the majority of

the selected girls used disposable sanitary pads this study noted low usage of sanitary pad.

Good knowledge of menstrual hygiene has influenced older adolescent age (15-19 years) as revealed in the study and was supported by Habtegiorgis et al. (2021), This study showed a significant association between age and good practice of menstrual hygiene ($R^2 = 0.97$, $P = 0.00$) while in a study carried out by Funmito et al. (2017) indicated that there is no statistically significant association between the age of adolescent and good practice of menstrual hygiene ($\chi^2=3.52$, $P=0.061$). In this study burying of used absorbent was low but Van Eijk et al. (2016) burying was more common, this may be due to the time it will take during the burying process and also the avoidance of been seen by other students. In this study girls had bath 3 times daily this was in line with Jagruti and Riddhi (2015), Shubha and Madhuri (2017). Hand washing with soap & water was presently low but at a high rate by Jagruti and Riddhi (2015), Shamima et al. (2013). This study showed adolescent school girls did not use sanitary pads during their menstruation period this was in line by Belayneh and Mekuriaw (2019). Some girls use tissue paper though at a low rate and was supported by Cajetan et al. (2016), Umeora and Egwuatu (2008). Students flushed used menstrual materials in the toilets at 1.46 which was in line with Lawan et al. (2010) in their study this may be because when flushed in the toilet no one will have access to it and they ignore the implication of blocking the drainage system.

Consequences: This study showed unavailability of menstrual hygiene facilities in schools as well as poor knowledge on the use of tissue paper, cotton wool during menstruation which is not safe, and the low practice of menstrual hygiene among students, this implies that those students are exposed to cases like fungal infections, reproductive tract infections, urinary tract infections, scabies in the vaginal area, rashes in the perianal area, bad odor, as well as environmental pollution, absent from school which has negative effects towards learning.

Implications: This review illustrates the need for Governments, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO), parents and teachers should intensify training discouraging students on the use of tissue paper, cotton wool during menstruation which is not safe to their health, and also consider improving the educational system by making facilities needed available as well as creating enabling environment during learning hours to improve students safety.

Conclusively, the study showed that 79.4% had good knowledge of menstrual hygiene expect, those whose age ranges from (15-19 years; 81.3%), those in class 2 (SS2) (80.7%), among others, unavailability of menstrual hygiene facilities in schools ($\bar{X}=2.47$, $SD=0.96$), Also, the result revealed that the grand mean of ($\bar{X}=2.34$, $SD=1.01$) which was lesser than the criterion mean of 2.50 revealed a low extent of practice, students whose age ranges from (10-14 years; $\bar{X}= 2.36$, $SD=0.98$), those of them in SS2 ($\bar{X}= 2.41$, $SD=1.01$), among others. However, age, class of study, had significant relationship

with menstrual hygiene knowledge and practice among senior secondary school students in Abia South Senatorial District.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were here by made:

1. Due to unavailability of menstrual hygiene facilities as seen in this study governments, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO) and individuals can take up the project of providing menstrual facilities in different public schools, such as borehole water, soap, menstrual pads, incinerators etc.
2. Based on age (10-14years) which showed a low level of knowledge and practice among others in the study, teachers, media, and parents should early introduce and teach about menstruation and the appropriate practices to the students even before their menstrual periods begins and also the effect it may lead to if not properly managed, hygiene practices and sex education should be constantly taught and monitored.
3. This study showed poor knowledge on proper drying of washed re-usable (thick clean white towel) materials in direct sunlight, this can be reversed if teachers should put up signage's, arts or cartoons in female toilets, encouraging female students on the right ways to dry their reusable material in direct sunlight and also the effects on the use of tissue paper, pieces, cotton wool and the long use of sanitary pads in schools, the correct instructions should be demonstrated.
4. Teacher should use moral instruction days and PTA meetings, to explain and

encourage female students as well as their parents or guardian on the need for menstrual hygiene practices and also give room for interaction section, this will improve their practice level regarding menstrual hygiene.

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